

APPLICATION OF HAMMICK AND ANDREWS EQUATION TO TERNARY MIXTURES. PART IV.

BY S. O. SHUKLA AND W. V. BHAGWAT

Ternary systems containing all liquids, such as ethyl acetate, benzene, carbon tetrachloride and toluene have been investigated and Hammick and Andrew's mixture law has been found applicable. Since for binary mixtures of these liquids the calculated and the observed values agree, the same is found to be true in ternary mixtures of these liquids.

In previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 179, 1945, 22, 311; 1947, 24, 231) it was shown that the expression,

$$P_m = (1-x-y) P_p + xP_x + yP_y$$

is applicable to ternary mixtures containing two solids and the observed results do not agree with the calculated ones but with those obtained in solutions of binary mixtures. In this paper the work is extended to ternary mixtures consisting of liquids only. At first the parachors of pure liquids individually have been determined and the results agree with the calculated values.

TABLE I

Liquid.	d.	r.	P _{obs.}	Liquid.	d.	r.	P _{obs.}
Benzene	0.8661	27.8	206.6	Toluene	0.8658	27.53	246.1
Ethyl acetate	0.8907	23.68	215.7	Ethyl acetate	1.578	27.19	223.3

Ethyl Acetate, Toluene and Benzene System

In the following tables parachor of ethyl acetate has been calculated which in the pure liquid state comes out to be 215.7.

TABLE II

4.3310 G. of ethyl acetate and 5.0836 g. of toluene dissolved in 4.1938 g. of benzene. x (ethyl acetate) = 0.3114; y (toluene) = 0.3493; $1-x-y$ (benzene) = 0.3393; $M_m = 86.06$.	3.5294 G. of ethyl acetate & 4.7076 g. of toluene dissolved in 6.644 g. of benzene. x (ethyl acetate) = 0.4824; y (toluene) = 0.2273; $1-x-y$ (benzene) = 0.2903; $M_m = 84.36$.
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Temp.	d.	r.	P _{m.}	P _{x.}	d.	r.	P _{m.}	P _{x.}
26°	0.8689	25.87	223.2	215.6	0.8677	26.87	221.4	218.6
30	0.8680	25.87	223.2	215.6	0.8645	26.42	221.3	218.2
35	0.8648	25.12	222.9	214.3	0.8600	25.70	220.9	217.6
40	0.8601	24.68	223.0	214.9	0.8550	25.12	220.9	217.6

6.6574 G. of ethyl acetate and 3.4918 g. of toluene dissolved in 3.4484 g. of benzene. x (ethyl acetate) = 0.4988; y (toluene) = 0.2368; $1-x-y$ (benzene) = 0.2764; $M_m = 86.22$.	4.3938 G. of ethyl acetate and 6.5866 g. of toluene dissolved in 4.0743 g. of benzene. x (ethyl acetate) = 0.2674; y (toluene) = 0.4118; $1-x-y$ (benzene) = 0.3208; $M_m = 86.71$.
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28°	0.8735	25.0	220.8	216.7	0.8715	25.8	225.3	215.0
30	0.8701	24.55	220.6	216.1	0.8641	25.35	225.2	214.7
35	0.8655	24.04	220.6	216.1	0.8602	25.0	225.4	215.4
40	0.8608	23.28	220.2	215.5	0.8566	24.55	225.3	215.0

TABLE II (contd.)

4.2866 G. of ethyl acetate and 4.5610 g. of toluene dissolved in 2.6976 g. of benzene. x (ethyl acetate)=0.3636; y (toluene)=0.3741; $1-x-y$ (benzene)=0.2623; $M_m=86.88$.					2.7904 G. of ethyl acetate and 4.5938 g. of toluene dissolved in 4.1746 g. of benzene. x (ethyl acetate)=0.2346; y (toluene)=0.3693; $1-x-y$ (benzene)=0.3961; $M_m=85.55$.				
Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	
26°	0.8714	25.69	224.5	215.2	0.8672	26.48	223.9	216.1	
30	0.8660	25.18	224.3	214.4	0.8640	25.94	223.0	216.8	
35	0.8641	24.66	224.1	214.1	0.8601	25.41	223.3	215.5	
40	0.8592	24.21	224.3	214.6	0.8562	24.83	222.9	215.9	

TABLE III

Ethyl acetate, benzene and carbon tetrachloride system.

4.4539 G. of ethyl acetate & 4.2892 g. of benzene dissolved in 8.2780 g. of CCl_4 . x (CCl_4)=0.3115; y (ethyl acetate)=0.3437; $1-x-y$ (benzene)=0.3448; $M_m=100.9$.					10.3378 G. of CCl_4 and 4.4578 g. of ethyl acetate dissolved in 4.1476 g. of benzene. x (CCl_4)=0.3924; y (ethyl acetate)=0.2962; $1-x-y$ (benzene)=0.3114; $M_m=110.8$.				
Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	
27°	1.117	25.74	215.6	224.6	1.158	26.1	216.6	225.2	
30	1.114	25.35	215.4	223.6	1.154	25.7	216.1	223.0	
35	1.109	24.99	215.6	224.6	1.148	25.23	216.3	224.4	
40	1.103	24.32	215.3	223.3	1.140	24.72	216.6	225.2	

7.5599 G. of CCl_4 and 4.8070 g. of ethyl acetate dissolved in 7.0302 g. of benzene. x (CCl_4)=0.2812; y (ethyl acetate)=0.4649; $M_m=100.1$.					7.8124 G. of CCl_4 and 6.9974 g. of ethyl acetate dissolved in 4.0080 g. of benzene. x (CCl_4)=0.3776; y (ethyl acetate)=0.4417; $1-x-y$ (benzene)=0.2807; $M_m=102.4$.				
Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	
27°	1.058	26.02	213.6	224.0	1.078	26.17	214.5	221.6	
30	1.055	25.59	213.3	222.9	1.076	25.7	214.3	219.6	
35	1.049	25.12	213.6	224.0	1.070	25.18	214.6	221.5	
40	1.043	24.6	213.7	224.0	1.063	24.55	214.6	221.5	

13.7202 G. of CCl_4 and 3.6604 g. of ethyl acetate dissolved in 3.6352 g. of benzene. x (CCl_4)=0.5060; y (ethyl acetate)=0.2294; $1-x-y$ (benzene)=0.2646; $M_m=119.8$.				
Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
27°	1.235	25.84	217.8	224.4
30	1.232	25.47	217.5	224.0
35	1.226	24.66	218.8	221.6
40	1.218	24.15	217.3	223.3